

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCHEDULED TRIBES IN INDIA : A STUDY**Mr. J. V. Padvi***Researcher**Assistant Professor,**Post Graduate Department of Political
Science, Moolji Jaitha College, Jalgaon***Dr. Vijay S. Tunte***Research Guide**Associate Professor,**Post Graduate Department of Political
Science, Pratap College, Amalner***Abstract :**

The large number of scheduled tribes groups in India. They are situated in the small areas like in mountains, forests and in some part of the river valleys, plain area. The total tribal groups in India are 705 and they have some subgroups too. According to the Indian Census, 2011, the population of tribal's is 8.6% of the total population of the country. The numbers of tribal groups in Maharashtra are 47 and the population of tribal's in Maharashtra is 9.28%. These groups are economically backward and have been away from civilian life.

The constitutional provisions of the Constitution of India have been made by the constitution makers for raising civilian life. Ministry of Tribal Affairs has been constituted to implement these provisions intensively. Also, the National Scheduled Tribal Commission has been set up. At the state level, the Ministry of Tribal Development has also been established. Through this ministry, various developmental programmes have been initiated to implement planned development up to the grassroot level.

Article 342, Indian Constitution, tribal groups are referred to as Scheduled Tribes. In order to develop these tribal communities politically and administratively, the reservation in political, administrative and co-operative have been made in the constitution of India. Some representative assembly constituencies at the state level have been reserved for the tribals as well as local self-government and co-operative institutions have been reserved for their representation. Accordingly, the attempts to implement strategic programmes at the constitutional level. Apart from this, women reservation policy has been introduced to bring tribal women ahead. This is a constitutional attempt to strengthen women. In addition to this, in the administrative area of the Indian Constitution, provision has been made to give opportunity to the tribal's to reserve seats in the central-state and other local self-government.

After 10 years of the Indian Constitution came into existence, the tribal's were expected to fully absorb all these political and administrative services through reservation. It has not been intensively implemented. Since, seven decades have gone by the process of continuation of the reservation process needs to be repeated. It shows that constitutional bodies have also been weak in achieving development. Therefore, it is always a challenge of developing the tribal sub-plan for the Indian Governmental system. This is the topic of contemplation of the fundamentals. Therefore, the concept of social science is leading to the formation of the key. The researcher has tried to study this subject.

Research objective :

- 1) To understand the concept of scheduled tribes development in India.
- 2) To study the developmental status of scheduled tribes in India.
- 3) To study of the constitutional bodies to scheduled tribes development.
- 4) To study the financial, health, agricultural, educational, environmental condition of Scheduled Tribes in India.

Study area of the research :

Till, now, an effort has been made to implement various strategic development schemes at National and State level for the development of Scheduled Tribes in India. To study its development. This is the study area of this research.

Research Methods :

The descriptive and comparative study methods have been used in this research. The secondary tools are based on the Data Collection. These include reports of the Ministry of Home Affairs, Ministry of Tribal Affairs, National Commission for Scheduled Tribes, various Governmental decisions, Circulars, Census of India 2011, reference books, newspaper, informative books, and the internet.

Hypothesis :

- 1) Many schemes are implemented for the development of Scheduled Tribes in India through the Government of India.
- 2) There has been no development of the Scheduled Tribes according constitutional provisions.

Identity of Scheduled Tribes :

Many researchers have used words such as Aboriginal, Primitive Tribes, Indigenous and Native, while studying tribal groups or communities. Each of these words has a social and political context. That can be said.

Definiation :-

Generally, 'A group or community resides in a geographical region or from time immemorial or aboriginal, is tribal.' Such broad definitions can be defined.

Scheduled Tribe in India :

In the Indian Constitution, the Constitutional Producers of India have referred to Adivasis as 'Scheduled Tribes'. There are approximately 705 Scheduled tribes in India and their subgroup is also (sub-caste). According to India census year 2011, the population of Scheduled Tribes is 8.6 percent. The Scheduled Tribes group resides in the harid areas of India's remote area, forest area, mountainous region and partly in the plains. This group is economically extremely backward. They have made separate provisions in the Constitution to parallel the development of their community, through these provisions, an official development of social, political, administrative and financial nature is intended.

Provisions mentioned in the Constitution of India regarding 'Scheduled Tribes' :

- 1) Article 366 (25), Indian Constitution : "Scheduled Tribes" means such tribes or tribal

communities or parts of or groups within such tribes or tribal communities as are deemed under article 342 to be Scheduled Tribes for the purpose of this Constitution.¹

- 2) Article 342 (1), Indian Constitution : The President³ [many with respect to any state² [or Union Territory], and where it is a state⁴ ***, after constitution with the governor⁵*** thereof,] by public notification⁶, specify the tribes or tribal communities or parts of or groups within tribes or tribal communities which shall for the purposes of this constitution be deemed to be Scheduled Tribes in relation to that State² [or Union territory, as the case may be].²
- 3) Article 342 (2), Indian constitution : Parliament may by law include in or exclude from the list of Scheduled Tribes specified in a notification issued under clause (1) any tribe or tribal community or part of a group within any tribe or tribal community, but save as aforesaid a notification issued under the said clause shall not be varied by any subsequent notification.³

Apart from this, various provisions have been made in the Indian Constitution for the development of Scheduled Tribes in India. According to 1999, Ministry of Tribal Affairs, Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment was formed. It is the Ministry of External Affairs; It is strategic, planning and coordinating. In addition, the components are nodal ministries at state level. Various development program or project programs are implemented in the form of Tribal sub-plans. Also planned programs like Integrated Tribal Development Project (ITDP), Modified Area Development Approach (MADA), Clusters, Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) and Dispersed Tribal Population Outside are implemented. These programs are done through the special central assistance (grant or subsidies). Grants are allotted likewise Education cost 40-50%, health 10-15%, agriculture, horticulture, animal husbandry (AH), fisheries, dairy and other primary sectors 20-30%, other income generating schemes to the augment tribal household economy 10-15% and administrative structure (including manpower) / <5-10% are done on the institutional framework and research studies.⁴

In 2003, the Constitution of India included Article 338 A by amending the Constitution of Article 338 of the Constitution of India. Accordingly, in 2004, the National Commission for Scheduled Tribes was set-up. The duties of this commission are as follows :

Duty of the National Commission of Scheduled Tribes

- a) To investigate and monitor all matters relating to the safeguards provided for the Scheduled Tribes under this Constitution or under any other law for the time being in force or under any order of the Government and to evaluate the working of such safeguards.
- b) To inquire into specific complaints with aspect to the deprivation of rights and safeguards of the Scheduled Tribes;
- c) To participate and advice on the planning process of socio-economic development of the Scheduled Tribes and to Evaluate the progress of their development under the union and any state;
- d) To present to the President, annually and at such other times as the commission may deem fit, reports upon the working of those safeguards;

- e) To make in such reports recommendation as to the measures that should be taken by the Union or any State for the effective implementation of those safeguards and other measures for the protection, welfare and socio-economic development of the Scheduled Tribes; and
- f) To discharge such other functions in relation to the protection, welfare and development and advancement of the Scheduled Tribes as the President may, subject to the provisions of any law made by parliament, by rule specify.

According to this, the development of Scheduled castes is expected to be done and the work of annihilation will be done.

Statistical Information on Development of Scheduled Tribes :

1) Poverty

Sr. No.	Position of Poverty	Percentage
1	Poverty Percentage of Poor (Rural)	46
2	Poverty Percentage of Poor (Urban)	35
3	Poverty Agricultural Labour (Rural)	61
4	Poverty Causal Labour (Urban)	64

(Source : *Development Challenges in extremist affected areas, Report of an expert group to planning commission, Government of India, New Delhi, April 2008, Page No. 04.*)

This table illustrates the ratio of poverty to scheduled tribes in India. This is a prescription. This raised question marks regarding the schedule of development of Scheduled Tribes.

2) Mortality and under nutrition

Sr. No.	Mortality and Under Nutrition	Percentage
1	Infront Mortality (Per 1000 Live births) 2005-06	44
2	Under five mortality 2005-06	96
3	Proportion (%) of Children with Anemia	79
4	Proportion of Underweight children	26

(Source : *Development Challenges in extremist affected areas, Report of an expert group to planning commission, Government of India, New Delhi, April 2008, Page No. 04.*)

The ratio of infant mortality in this table is 44 per thousand. The rate of mortality intake of 5 years is 96% in these the proportion of Anemia's Disease is 79%, while 26% mortality is due to underweight. This information is completely flawless. That is, in order to improve this situation, the Government has taken a number of helpful measures in health and economically large scale. Their implementation is also successful. But this was successful on paper. However, the data from this table shows a question mark on the implementation of measures, their functions and liabilities.

3) Access to Agricultural land and capital assets

Sr. No.	Type	Percentage
1	Value of Assets per HH in Rupees (1992)	52,660
2	Percentage of self-employed cultivators	48%
3	Percentage of wage labour (Rural)	49%
4	Percentage of Casual Labour (Urban)	26%

(Source : *Development Challenges in extremist affected areas, Report of an expert group to planning commission, Government of India, New Delhi, April 2008, Page No. 04.*)

In this chart, every scheduled tribe family gets the same annual income of Rs. 52,660/- (from the 1992 report), Also, employment is not available adequately.

4) Literacy Rate

Sr. No.	Men / Women	India	Maharashtra
1	Men	68.53%	74.3%
2	Women	49.35%	57.0%
3	Total	58.96%	65.7%

Source : *Tribal Profile at a Glance, May 2004 (Registrar General of India, Census 2011)*

This table indicates that the literacy rate of Scheduled Tribes in India is just 58.96%. Which is less compared to India's Development Policies. The literacy rate of Scheduled Tribes in India is less than 50%. In Maharashtra, the total literacy rate is 65.7% out of which is the female literacy ratio is 57%. That is, this ratio is very low, 40% to 50% of the Central Tribes Affairs Ministry is spending on education. After that, several project educational programs are planned at the state level. But the government does not feel interested in their actual situation for the development of Scheduled Tribes.

5-1) Percentage of Scheduled Tribes households in various position

Sr. No.	Position	India	Maharashtra
1	Good	39.8%	48.0%
2	Livable	53.9%	44.1%
3	Dilapidated	06.3%	07.9%
4	Total	95.6%	100.0%

Of these 2)

Sr. No.	Material of roof	India	Maharashtra
1	Grass / Thatch / Bamboo / Mud	18.6%	9.7%
2	G.I./ Metal / Asbestors / Sheets	19.5%	30.4%
3	Grass / Thatch / Bamboo	16.2%	19.9%
4	Mud / Unburnt brick	48.0%	33.6%

(Source : *House Listing and Housing Census, 2011*)

This table indicates that, 95.6% of Scheduled Tribes families have houses. But they have large number of crude houses. Therefore, it may be time to face any catastrophe occasion. e.g. It was time to lose the same to many families in Malin Village of Ambegaon taluka in Pune district of Maharashtra on 30th July, 2015.

6) Main Source of Drinking Water

1) Drinking Source

Sr. No.	Water Source	India	Maharashtra
1	Covered well	01.9	03.6
2	Uncovered well	19.8	21.1
3	Handpump	40.6	19.2
4	Tubewell / Borehole	07.8	03.9
5	Spring	03.1	01.4
6	River / Canal	02.0	01.0
7	Tank / Pond / Lake	01.1	00.5
8	Other	01.2	00.9
9	Tap water from treated source	-	34.2
10	Tap water from untreated source	-	14.1

2) Water Source Location

Sr. No.	Location of Drinking water	India	Maharashtra
1	Within Premises	18.0%	33.9%
2	Near Premises	47.6%	43.3%
3	Away	34.3%	22.8%

(Source : House Listing and Housing Census, 2011)

Both tables indicate that many scheduled tribe families in India have to depend on different source of water. It is unlikely that the water is contaminated, chemical or portable. Therefore, it can be time to face many disorders. According to this information, 34.03% of Scheduled Tribes have to bring water from outside the living area. But 22.08% Scheduled Tribes families in Maharashtra have to take water from outside the living premises. This is a disastrous situation for Scheduled Tribes in India.

7) Main Source of Lighting

Sr. No.	Source of Lighting	India	Maharashtra
1	Electricity	50.0%	59.8%
2	Kerosens	47.3%	36.2%
3	Solar Energy	01.1%	01.2%
4	Other oil	00.3%	03.3%
5	Any other	00.0%	00.4%
6	No lighting	01.0%	02.0%

(Source : House Listing and Housing Census, 2011)

50% of Scheduled Tribes families in India do not have access to electricity. More than 40% of Scheduled Tribes families in Maharashtra do not have electricity. 47.3% in India and 36.2% of Scheduled Tribes in Maharashtra have to depend on Kerosene. So many Scheduled Tribes Families have to spend their life in a dark environment. This is the obvious truth.

8) Number of households not having latrine facility

1) Within the Premises

Sr. No.	Latrine Facility	India	Maharashtra
1	Not have	79.4%	69.9%

2) Alternative Source

Sr. No.	Source	India	Maharashtra
1	Public Latrine	02.4%	10.2%
2	Open	76.9%	59.7%

(Source : House Listing and Housing Census, 2011)

This table shows that, 20% scheduled tribes families have latrine facility in India. While this ratio of Maharashtra is 30%. However, the public latrine facility is not available even through it is necessary. 76.9% in India and 59.7% in Maharashtra the Scheduled Tribes families use open space for latrine. They do not even have the capability to create their own facilities. However, the government is giving subsidy to some extent financially for built of latrines recently. But this facility is not available to innumerable families. The above information is questionable.

9) Number of households having bathing facility

Sr. No.	Material of roof	India	Maharashtra
1	Bathroom	15.1%	37.2%
2	Enclosure without roof	14.2%	29.9%
3	No bathing facility	70.7%	32.9%

(Source : House Listing and Housing Census, 2011)

Above table shows that, 70.7% in India and 32.9% in Maharashtra does not have bathing facility of Scheduled Tribes families. These families need to have baths in the rivers, lakes, canals, sea coast, well etc. This one dissecting picture become clear.

10) Waste water outlet connected to

Sr. No.	Drainage	India	Maharashtra
1	Closed Drainage	04.8%	15.7%
2	Open Drainage	15.8%	25.7%
3	No Drainage	79.4%	58.6%

(Source : House Listing and Housing Census, 2011)

In this table contains 97.4% of India and 58.6% of Scheduled Tribe families in Maharashtra do not have drainage system. Therefore, the water used for various reasons comes in open space. They may be the reason for inviting various ailments. From this, scheduled tribes have to remain aware of various disease. It is clear that.

11) Type of Fuel used for cooking

Sr. No.	Material of roof	India	Maharashtra
1	Fire wood	80.5	70.0
2	Crop reside	06.5	05.0
3	Cowdung Cake	02.7	01.0
4	Coal, Lignite, Charcoal	00.9	00.2
5	Kerosene	01.1	03.9
6	LPG / PNG	07.3	18.9
7	Electricity	00.1	00.1
8	Biogas	00.2	00.2
9	Any Other	00.6	00.1
10	No cooking	00.2	00.5

(Source : House Listing and Housing Census, 2011)

This table shows that, 80.05% in India and 70% of Scheduled Tribes in Maharashtra are dependent on wood for cooking purpose. This is the worst picture in the country.

12) Total number of household availing banking facility

Sr. No.	Baking Services	India	Maharashtra
1	Available	44.2%	47.9%

(Source : House Listing and Housing Census, 2011)

This table shows that around 45.80% of Scheduled Tribe families in Maharashtra and 48.10% of the Scheduled Tribes households have no banking services. Because this bank services is located in a large number of cities. There is a decrease in rural areas. Recently, to forced to people to has bank accounts for governmental benefits. But there are many difficulties in getting this service. That can be said.

Conclusion :

There is a large number of Scheduled Tribes in India. Development of these scheduled tribes in accordance with India's development policy has not been achieved. About 70 years have passed since India became independent. However, the percentage of growth is relatively small compared to other communities. Even after the creation of separate system for the development work, the provision of full cost could not be eliminated by the scheduled tribes. From this, the negative questions related to development are raised by the researchers.

To eliminate this tribal, policies and governance need to work with a lot of will, responsibility and accountability. In addition to this, the development of the scheduled tribes needs to be done by volunteering to support the various volunteer mechanisms, and to increase social participation. Also, those who represent Scheduled Tribes also need to work and stay committed to social work.

References :

- 1) The Constitution of India, (Part IXI – Miscellaneous, Art. 366), Pg. No. 238.
- 2) The Constitution of India, (Part XVI – Special Provisions Relating to Certain Classes, Art. 341-342), Pg. No. 211.
- 3) The Constitution of India, (Part XVI – Special Provisions Relating to Certain Classes, Art. 341-342), Pg. No. 211.
- 4) <http://www.ncst.nic.in>.
- 5) NCST Handbook, 2015, Pg.No. 9-10.